

Additional File 7. mMSC distribution between day 14 and 30. (a) From day 24 onwards for IC-injected mice, it was necessary to increase the scale by two orders of magnitude (BLI scale $1.0 \times 10^7 - 1.0 \times 10^8$ p/s/cm²/sr, orange frame) compared to that in Fig. 4 to enable visualisation of the very strong signals resulting from rapidly proliferating mMSCs. **(b)** Using the original scale (see Fig. 4: $1.0 \times 10^5 - 1.0 \times 10^6$ p/s/cm²/sr), signals could be detected by day 24 in one (out of 3) IV-injected mice. **(c,e)** Representative *in vivo* and corresponding **(d,f)** *ex vivo* organ images at day 30. **(d)** Small spots of bioluminescence signal could be detected in some of the organs of IC-injected BALB/c SCID mice (arrows), but the scale had to be lowered to $1.0 \times 10^4 - 1.0 \times 10^5$ p/s/cm²/sr (blue frame) in order to be able to display these weak signals. **(e)** Two out of three IV-administered BALB/c SCID mice did not show any signals at day 30 *in vivo* using the standard scale (green frame), however, corresponding **(f)** organ imaging showed small foci of bioluminescence signals in the lungs (arrows).